

UDK 615 (497.11)

ISSN 0004-1963 (Štampano izd.)

ISSN 2217-8767 (Online)

ARHIV ZA FARMACIJU

Godina 69

Broj 4 SUPLEMENT

Beograd, 2019.

ČASOPIS SAVEZA FARMACEUTSKIH UDRUŽENJA SRBIJE

Prvi simpozijum Sekcije za farmaceutske nauke SFUS

Od ideje do kliničke primene: Savremena istraživanja u farmaciji

Novi Sad, 26. septembar 2019.

First symposium of the SFUS Section for pharmaceutical sciences

From idea to clinical application: Current pharmaceutical research

Novi Sad, 26. September 2019.

4/2019

ARH. FARM. Godina 69 Br.4 SUPLEMENT Strana S1 - S100 Beograd

ANTIHIPERGLIKEMIJSKI POTENCIJAL VRSTA RODA *HYPERICUM*

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Uzimajući u obzir porast incidence dijabetesa tip 2 na svetskom nivou, od izuzetne važnosti je potraga za novim agensima koji pokazuju sposobnost da utiču na postprandijalnu hiperglikemiju.

Različiti proizvodi prirodnog porekla, koji sadrže fenole i flavonoide kao sekundarne metabolite, pokazali su određenu sposobnost inhibicije α -amilaze i α -glukozidaze, tj. enzima uključenih u prve korake razgradnje ugljenih hidrata u ljudskom organizmu. Stoga, cilj ovog istraživanja bilo je *in vitro* ispitivanje antiamilaznog i antiglukozidaznog potencijala vodeno-alkoholnih ekstrakata različitih vrsta roda *Hypericum*. Konkretno, tokom perioda 2011-2016. godine na teritoriji centralnog dela Balkanskog poluostrva prikupljeno je ukupno 117 uzoraka, predstavnika 29 različitih taksona roda *Hypericum*. Sposobnost inhibicije odabranih enzima od strane vodeno-alkoholnih ekstrakata je ispitana spektrofotometrijski uz primenu „starch azure[®]” i p-nitrofenil- α -D-glukozida kao supstrata za α -amilazu i α -glukozidazu. Akarboza je upotrebljena kao pozitivna kontrola u oba test-sistema. Dobijeni rezultati su pokazali da ispitani ekstrakti pokazuju manju sposobnost inhibicije α -amilaze u odnosu na α -glukozidazu. Tačnije, više od 80% ispitanih ekstrakata je pokazalo veću sposobnost inhibicije α -glukozidaze u odnosu na akarbozu, dok su se kao naročiti inhibitori ovog enzima pokazali ekstrakti *H. androsaemum*, *H. calycinum*, *H. umbellatum* i *H. triquetrifolium* ($IC_{50} \leq 10 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

Zahvalnica: Istraživanje je sprovedeno u okviru Projekta Ministarstva prosvete, nauke i tehnološkog razvoja (OI 172058) „Biološki aktivni prirodni proizvodi kao potencijalni izvori novih lekova i dijetetskih suplemenata”.

THE ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC POTENTIAL OF *HYPERICUM* SPECIES

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Considering the rising incidence of diabetes type 2 on global level, of paramount importance is screening for agents which have the ability to affect the postprandial hyperglycemia. Different products of natural origin, containing phenolics and flavonoids as secondary metabolites, have showed certain potential to inhibit α -amylase and α -glucosidase, enzymes included in the first steps of carbohydrates digestion in human body. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate *in vitro* anti-amylase and anti-glucosidase potential of water-alcoholic extracts of different *Hypericum* species. Specifically, during the period 2011-2016, total of 117 samples representing 29 *Hypericum* taxa were collected at the territory of central part of Balkan Peninsula. The potential of prepared extracts to inhibit selected enzymes was evaluated spectrophotometrically by use of Starch azure[®] and p-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucoside as substrates for α -amylase and α -glucosidase, respectively. Also, acarbose was used as positive control in both assays. The obtained results showed that the tested *Hypericum* extracts were generally stronger inhibitors of α -glucosidase than α -amylase. Specifically, more than 80% of the examined extracts showed greater inhibitory potential of α -glucosidase than acarbose, while the most promising effect was recorded in extracts prepared from *H. androsaemum*, *H. calycinum*, *H. umbellatum* i *H. triquetrifolium* ($IC_{50} \leq 10 \mu\text{g/mL}$).

Acknowledgements: Project of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia (Grant No 172058) „The biologically active natural products as potential sources of new medicines and dietary supplements“ supported this research.